

IMPORTANCE OF USING DIDACTIC MATERIALS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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ABSTRACT

It is an important task to interest young schoolchildren in reading books. The first outlook of a child devoted to studying is formed, the foundations of literacy are laid. This article considers a number of ways to implement the task, including the possibility of using didactic games.

INTRODUCTION

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education is widely implemented. With the honor of independence, a wide opportunity was given to carry out independent deep reforms in the public education system of our country. One of such reforms is aimed at improving students' speech culture. The correct formation of a child's speech is mainly observed in primary school and is completely improved when he goes to secondary school.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Didactic games are a method of teaching that is suitable for the age and capabilities of primary school students. They serve as the main means of activating passive children, boldly performing various tasks in the team. Didactic games help children to combine their interests with the interests of the community, to help each other, to be happy about the success of their friends, to find the content of good relationships, and to form positive qualities such as honesty and sincerity. Didactic games enhance children's intellectual activities, children use the knowledge they have acquired during training.

Didactic games are considered practical activities of children, they create life conditions for them to use their acquired knowledge in various ways.

The team game, which is played by dividing into certain roles, requires children to obey strict rules and perform certain tasks. Such games educate and develop positive qualities such as obedience to rules and discipline in children. For example, in the game "*Jumpers*", before the game starts, the teacher offers to remember animals like frog, rabbit, monkey, which like to jump. Then, sometimes turning into a frog, sometimes a monkey, he invites them to jump while singing the following song.

Integrative games are also a common type of game, which has a two-way character. This method allows, on the one hand, to take into account the appreciation of childhood, and on the other hand, to create conditions for the initial educational activity of a primary school student.

This game style is designed for the child's closest level of development and allows to combine emotional and rational understanding. That is, the process of engaging in mutual communication and teaching a foreign language involves the simultaneous completion of tasks aimed at the child's personal development and the integration of various types of activities (visual, musical-rhythmic, theatrical).

Situational games include role-playing games that organize situations on one or another topic. They, in turn, are divided into games of a reproductive nature, in which children use typical, standard dialogues according to one or another situation.

Speech is a type of human activity, the implementation of thoughts based on linguistic means. Speech fulfills the functions of communication and communication, expressing one's thoughts with emotion and influencing others.

A well-developed speech is one of the important means of a person's active activity in society, and for a student, speech is a tool for successful learning at school. Children should be taught to speak fluently from an early age [3].

In order to develop speech through didactic games, it is necessary to use methods and techniques that help students in active acquisition of pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction and connected speech.

The purpose of mother tongue education is to teach students to think and use the means of expression of the language in accordance with the purpose and in accordance with the norms of this language.

It is important to teach children to speak fluently, use beautiful words in their speech, and express their thoughts freely. In elementary grades, students acquire theoretical and practical knowledge during all lessons, as well as oral speech through the correct construction of sentences, rules of interaction, expression of ideas, re-creative storytelling, memorization of poems. The songs have also been developed.

Speech cannot be separated from thinking, speech develops on the basis of thinking [4].

Reading and native language classes effectively help enrich children's vocabulary and teach them how to structure speech.

The study lesson and related excursions provide students with nature, people's life and work. In this lesson, the student creates ample opportunities for speech, its formation and growth. In other lessons of the primary class, students' speech is enriched with various words.

If a plan for the development of students' oral speech is organized in primary grades, if the activities in this area are carried out regularly, it will affect the whole body of the student, his feelings, imagination, will and character, and finally, the activity and ability of thinking. It is very important for the fluent expression of speech. In this way, through the development of speech skills, the ability to speak correctly and express clear, logical thoughts is formed. It realizes their creative activity and talents by developing them [5].

In order to develop the oral speech of students, teachers should strengthen their vocabulary in all classes by teaching them to actively use words in speech based on a specific plan. Students cannot think clearly and fluently without having enough vocabulary.

Each new word learned increases the students' vocabulary and expands the possibilities of expressing their thoughts. Therefore, it is necessary to continuously work with students on acquiring words and their meanings. In this case, it is very important to gradually absorb the words of the student into the speech of the student in a continuous approach. For example:

Face green compact round Aft zangori kikkina circle Bashara kok jajji londa

The teacher should not forget to teach the students that the words are necessary elements of the text. In order to prepare students for oral presentation, a number of special tasks specific to general speech should be carried out, and well-organized practical training should help to improve the student's oral speech. This is especially important for students to master. If it is difficult to understand the meaning of words, it is very important to use sentences.

The task of teachers is to determine the number of statements and essays in the planning of speech development for academic quarters, as well as to determine the nature of oral and written works and their place in the system of correct writing exercises. It is intended to improve skills in the field of written speech on the basis of developing oral speech. When children perform oral exercises, the teacher gives instructions on the content and appearance of the statement, helps to eliminate the mistakes made.

CONCLUSION

First of all, we should emphasize that it is important to organize didactic games in the development of students' speech. Because playful lessons are interesting and popular for students. Because of these games, the student will be interested in attending school and classes. In addition, those who try to answer in every lesson, who think carefully and then speak, are very attentive and changeable to every idea delivered by the teacher. In the current conditions, where education has become the priority of the state policy, the development of students' speech is especially important. Speech development is a necessary condition for personality formation. Therefore, the problem of speech development is always in the center of attention in primary education.

REFERENCES:

1. Amínov M.N., Majidov A.M. Education (encyclopedia for parents and teachers) T.: National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan "State, 2010.
2. Issues of speech culture formation in the educational process. Materials of the 5th regular conference from Uzbekistan. T.: "East", 2019.
3. Ghulomov A., Qabílova B. Speech development training. T.: "Teacher", 2015. Need to share.
4. Shodmonova Sh. Educational pedagogy. - T.: 2018. - B. 128,129.
5. Utekhina A. N. Ínostranny zyzyk v doshkolnom vozraste. Theory and practice. "Flinta", "Nauka". - M.: 2017. - p.125